

STRUCTURAL PREDICTION OF INJECTION MOLDED LONG FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS BASED ON PROCESS INDUCED FIBER MICROSTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Short fiber reinforced thermoplastics are used extensively due to their high mechanical properties and low processing costs. Long fiber reinforced thermoplastics (LFT) show an even more interesting property profile and are used more and more often for structural parts. However, processing is not as simple and their anisotropic properties resulting from the fiber microstructure pose a challenge with regard to the engineering design process. To reliably predict the structural mechanical properties of LFT, it is necessary to investigate a method that allows comprehensive consideration of the existing fiber microstructure within the engineering design process. For this purpose, a micromechanical approach developed at IKT has been extended to include the necessary process variables and the associated models.

1 INTRODUCTION

The wide variety of particular properties of plastics are widely utilized within the engineering design process and for the processing of parts. Fiber reinforced plastics are in general gaining importance due to the increasing demand for lightweight materials especially driven by stricter emission standards in the automotive industry.

Discontinuous fiber reinforced plastics combine high mechanical properties and high design flexibility with low manufacturing costs compared to other lightweight materials [1]. Therefore, ample research concerning short and long fiber reinforced plastics is in progress. The exploitation of the reinforcement potential within injection molding process can be increased by the use of long fibers. However, major challenges for long fiber reinforced plastic persist in the engineering design process and processing of the inhomogeneous, anisotropic materials.

Purposeful virtual engineering and a reliable prediction of the structural mechanical properties of long fiber reinforced thermoplastics (LFT) requires a holistic consideration of the given fiber microstructure. The coupling of process and structure simulation, also known as integrative simulation, builds the common basis. Thereby the calculation of process-induced anisotropy due to the local fiber orientation distribution counts to a certain extent towards this standard [2]. Whereas the locally varying fiber microstructure properties length and fraction have not yet been taken into account, or only to a limited extent.

2 STATE OF THE ART

During processing of discontinuous fiber reinforced plastics, a specific fiber microstructure is formed within the part cavity which depends on the material, the geometry of the molded part and the process settings. This microstructure mainly determines the part's properties. With suitable accuracy of the predicted fiber microstructure, the resulting anisotropic mechanical properties can be reliably calculated. Thus the part behavior can be determined in structure simulations.

2.1 Mechanical Properties

The resulting part properties of fiber reinforced materials are mainly determined by process induced fiber microstructure and its properties (Figure 1), such as

- fiber orientation,
- fiber length and diameter,
- fiber concentration and
- fiber matrix adhesion.

Figure 1 Influence of fiber orientation, length and concentration on the resulting mechanical properties

The increase in the respective fiber properties also leads to an increase in mechanical properties of the composite material, such as stiffness, strength and impact strength [3]. Only at high fiber concentrations can a decrease in strength and impact strength be observed above a specific threshold value. The stiffness, on the other hand, can be increased up to the saturation level. However, the properties of the fiber microstructure, especially in case of discontinuously reinforced plastics, can usually not only be influenced to a very limited extent, but are rather a result of processing.

2.2 Process Induced Fiber Microstructure

In molding processes in which plastic melts are used to produce parts, such as injection molding, a flow field is formed inside the cavity during part filling that depends on material, part geometry and process settings. This varies not only along the flow direction, for example through cooling effects, but also along the part thickness or the flow gap height of the flow, as shown in Figure 2. Due to this velocity profile, characteristic layers are formed along the part thickness in which the fibers

- are aligned differently (fiber orientation),
- break more frequently (fiber length) or
- migrate evenly (fiber concentration).

These individual properties also affect each other. Due to the interaction of the fibers, the fiber orientation depends on the fiber length and concentration, which also applies to interchanged dependencies. A characteristic profile is created inside a part, which can be subdivided into a core layer and two shear or skin layers. The specific characteristic ratio of the layers is determined by the quotient of the individual layer thicknesses and is generally referred to as the core-to-skin ratio.

Figure 2: Locally varying fiber microstructure along the normalized part thickness

2.3 Experimental Determination of Fiber Microstructure

The description of the process-induced fiber microstructure can be done by the three properties fiber orientation, length (or diameter) and concentration. The latter properties are described as scalar quantities (fiber mass fraction ψ or fiber volume fraction φ as well as fiber length l_f or fiber diameter d_f), whereas fiber orientation is mostly used as orientation tensor A of the second order according to Advani and Tucker [4].

In order to be able to provide a statistically representative statement about the existing fiber microstructure on the macroscopic level (entire part or local), an entire volume consisting of an ensemble of individual fibers is often analyzed. For a certain volume or element in which several fibers are present, a discrete fiber length distribution exists in the case of the fiber length. This can be described either by an approximated distribution function or as averaged values. The weight- or number-averaged fiber length \bar{l}_W, \bar{l}_N according to formula (1) is often used as a scalar quantity. The aspect ratio a_R , the quotient of fiber length and fiber diameter, can then be determined from these two information.

$$\bar{l}_N = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n N_i l_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n N_i} \quad \text{bzw.} \quad \bar{l}_W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n N_i l_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n N_i l_i} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the fiber volume fraction φ can be calculated locally as an area or volume comparison of the fibers for a defined cross-sectional area A_{tot} or the volume V_{tot} to be analyzed.

$$\varphi = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i}{A_{tot}} \quad \text{bzw.} \quad \varphi = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n V_i}{V_{tot}} \quad (2)$$

The orientation tensor describes the main orientation of all fibers in a defined volume or element via a probability density function $\Psi(p)$. The orientation tensor A is calculated as an integral over all possible fiber orientations from the distribution function of the fibers $\Psi(p)$ and the dyadic product of the unit vectors p .

$$A = a_{ij} = \oint p_i p_j \Psi(p) dp = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Numerous different methods exist to determine the existing fiber microstructure, such as ultrasound methods, optical methods like grinding pattern analysis [4, 5] or X-ray and computer tomography [6]. However, all methods are usually associated with high efforts and therefore used less frequently.

2.4 Process Simulation

In order to predict the fiber orientation, length and concentration by means of current simulation methods, it is necessary to calculate the flow field in the part. Within the process simulation the continuity equation and the equations of momentum and energy are solved numerically. This is usually done using the finite volume method. For the processing of polymer melts, the non-Newtonian flow behavior is additionally described using a rheological state equation (viscosity model).

The efficient calculation of the fiber orientation is usually based on statistical approaches using the orientation tensor [4]. The corresponding calculation models are mainly based on the extension of the Jeffery Model [7] by Folgar and Tucker. Current injection molding solvers use combined model extensions such as the iARD (improved Anisotropy Rotary Diffusion) and RPR model (Retarding Principal Rate) according to Tseng et al [8]. The model can be used for both short and long fiber reinforced thermoplastics [9] and is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{A} = \dot{A}_{HD} + \dot{A}_{iARD}(C_i, C_m) + \dot{A}_{RPR}(\alpha) \quad (4)$$

with A , the 2nd order orientation tensor, C_i , the fiber-fiber interaction coefficient, C_m , the fiber-matrix interaction coefficient, and α , the deceleration parameter. Thus, in total, three model parameters C_i , C_m and α remain for model calibration.

In addition to the orientation models, different model approaches exist nowadays to predict the

process-induced fiber breakage or the resulting fiber length, such as the model according to Phelps et. al. [10]. This model consists of a formula for preserving the entire fiber length and a formula describing fiber breakage. The number- or weight-averaged fiber length according to formula (1) can be used. In case of a fiber break, the fiber of length l_j is divided into two shorter fragments l_k and l_l , whose total length $l_i = l_k + l_l$ must be preserved. The time-related change of the number of fibers N_i with the fiber length l_i can be determined by the following conservation equation.

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = -P_i N_i + \sum_k R_{ik} N_k \quad (5)$$

The probability that fiber breakage occurs is evaluated as a loss (fiber breakage rate P_i) and the probability that longer fibers break to the fiber length l_i is evaluated as a gain (fiber growth rate R_{ik}). Three variable parameters remain for calibration: the fracture coefficient C_B , the fracture profile parameter S and the flow resistance coefficient ζ .

To predict fiber migration in polymer melts, several model approaches exist. The SB model (Suspension Balance) from Morris and Boulay [11] is mostly used in current simulation programs. The model was developed on the basis of investigations by Nott and Brady [12] on two-phase flows. In the model the fiber migration is determined in connection with the particle size, the maximum particle concentration, the viscosity and a particle stress, which can be induced by shear as well as normal stress.

To describe the migration of fibers, the mass and the pulse balance for both phases are used. The mass balance for the particles is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} + \langle u \rangle \cdot \nabla V_f = -\nabla \cdot j_{\perp} \quad \text{with} \quad j_{\perp} = V_f (U_p - \langle u \rangle). \quad (5)$$

V_f is the fiber volume fraction, $\langle u \rangle$ the average viscosity of the suspension and j_{\perp} the particle flow relative to the mean suspension movement. The mean velocity of the particle phase is given by U_p . The model parameters, the exponent n of the sedimentation function [13] (particle friction), the fiber length l_f and diameter l_d or the effective particle radius a [14] and the fiber volume fraction V_f must be specified for application.

2.5 Structural Simulation

To reduce computational effort, the models to predict the mechanical properties of inhomogeneous materials are based on a homogenization of the microstructure to the effective properties on the macroscopic level. Micromechanical models provided by Tandon-Weng [15] are usually used to predict the local composite stiffness. The latter is based on the theories of Eshelby and Mori-Tanaka. These calculations provide the engineering constants of a volume element with a unidirectional orientation of fibers inside a matrix. The input values for the calculation are the aspect ratio a_R and the volume fraction V_f of the fibers, and also the respective stiffness E , shear moduli G and Poisson's ratios ν of the fiber and the matrix. The orientation averaging [4] calculates the stiffness matrix C while taking the existing or predicted fiber orientation tensors A into account. This is leading to an anisotropic stiffness matrix of the material.

Alongside to a global defined single value for fiber length or aspect ratio, Nguyen et. al. [16] proposed an approach to account for a global fiber length distribution by micromechanical models. To predict the stiffness matrix of the unidirectional composite, the fiber length distribution described by Weibull's probability density function is taken into account. While the distribution can be calculated even by number they used it by weight with reasonable results. A further approach is based on the consideration of local averaged fiber length, which is calculated by using the fiber breakage model within the process simulation, to predict both stiffness and strength [17].

Due to the complexity of failure behavior of fiber-reinforced plastics, the strength characteristics are generally difficult to predict. However, the local composite strength can be calculated by using the critical fiber length l_c defined by Kelly-Tyson [18]

$$l_c = \frac{\sigma_f d_f}{2\tau_y} \quad (8)$$

where σ_f is the strength and d_f the diameter of the fibers and τ_y is the maximum shear stress at the interface. To calculate the tensile strength in the direction of fiber it is proposed to integrate the fiber length distribution in form of a density function, like shown in the following equation.

$$\sigma = \eta_0 V_f \sigma_f \left(\int_0^{l_c} f(l) \left[\frac{l}{2l_c} \right] dl + \int_{l_c}^{\infty} f(l) \left[1 - \frac{l_c}{2l} \right] dl \right) + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (9)$$

η_0 is the fiber orientation factor which is taking the fiber orientation into account and $f(l)$ represents the density function of fiber length. σ_m and σ_f are the strength of the matrix and fiber, respectively. V_f is the fiber volume fraction. Based on the work of Cox, Fukuda and Chou [19] presented a method to calculate the fiber orientation factor η_0 by using a probability density function of the fiber orientation.

For example, a reverse engineering approach as described in [20] can be used to calibrate the micromechanical models. In an iterative loop, the input variables of the micromechanical models are adapted until the predicted results correspond to the experimental measured values.

The mesh topology for process and structure simulations often greatly varies because of different requirements for the solver. Due to this, it is in general necessary to translate the calculated results from the process simulation onto the structural mesh. This translation can be made by comparing both of the computational meshes by means of the Delaunay-triangulation as described in [21].

2.6 Objectives

A reliable prediction of the structural mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced plastics, especially of long fiber-reinforced thermoplastics (LFT), is only possible in most cases with full consideration of the existing fiber microstructure. Current methods for the engineering design process of a part are based on the coupling of process and structure simulation by means of different homogenization approaches in which individual properties of the fiber microstructure are taken into account. However, there is no approach in which a holistic consideration of the fiber microstructure is realized. The aim of this study is to develop such an approach and to test its application. Furthermore, the consideration should not be limited to a simulative data basis, but should also include experimental measured data as a basis.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

For the experiments, injection molded plates according to DIN EN ISO 294-5 with dimensions of 80 mm x 80 mm x 4 mm are used. Tensile test specimens of type 1BA are cut out of the plates, parallel (0°), vertical (90°) and in 45° orientation to the direction of flow according to DIN EN ISO 527-2, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Fiber orientation tensor (left), double plate with marked tensile test specimens (right)

A long fiber reinforced polypropylene from TechnoCompound GmbH, Bad Sobernheim, Germany is used as material. The compounds are 10 mm long rod shaped pellets with a varied fiber mass fraction of 20 %, 40 % and 60 % of the product type TechnoFiber.

The plates are injection molded with a constant injection speed of 30 cm³/s, a holding pressure of 600 bar, a melt temperature of 230 °C and a mold temperature of 80 °C on an Allrounder 520S 1600-400 injection molding machine from Arburg, Lossburg, Germany.

3.1 Mechanical Characterization

Mechanical characterization is carried out by standard elongation controlled tensile tests according to DIN EN ISO 527-1. A universal tensile testing machine of type 1455 by Zwick/Roell, Ulm, Germany, is used to measure at least five valid repetitions at standard atmosphere (25 °C, 50 %). The test speed is 5 mm/min and the Young's modulus is determined at a speed of 1 mm/min.

3.2 Microstructural Analysis

The microstructure of the specimens is analyzed at the positions shown in Figure 3 with a sample size of 8 mm x 8 mm x 4 mm. The fiber orientation and concentration are determined with a μ CT-scan at the Polymer Engineering Center of the University of Wisconsin, Madison. The analysis was performed with an 800 μ CT Metrotome from Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany. The following parameters are used: Voltage 110 V, Current 70 A, Amplification 8, Projections 1080. The parameters are chosen to ensure that the resolution corresponds to about half the fiber diameter (approx. 16 μ m). The samples were mounted on a turntable and projections of a complete 360° rotation were recorded. The analysis was carried out with the VG Studio Max software from Volume Graphics, Heidelberg, Germany. The fiber orientation and concentration along the part thickness can thus be evaluated. A detailed explanation of the measuring method can be found in the work of Goris [23].

The fiber length is determined according to the method described in [24] in accordance with DIN EN ISO 3451 at positions A, B and C as well as the nozzle outlet of the plastification unit (red), as shown in Figure 3 on the right. Due to this measuring method, no evaluation along the part thickness is possible.

3.3 Process Simulation

The process simulation is performed with the software Moldex3D® of the CoreTech System company, Chupei City, Taiwan, version R15.0. The required mesh is generated by Rhinoceros 5 from Robert McNeel & Associates, Seattle, USA and is shown in Figure 4 (left). The plates are meshed with a structured grid consisting of 21 hexahedral elements along the thickness of the part, whereas tetrahedral elements are used for the runner system and sprue. The viscosity of the individual materials is determined by means of high-pressure capillary and rotational rheometry and approximated with the power law. The respective model parameters for the prediction of the fiber microstructure are determined by an iterative optimization of the simulation results compared to the experimental measured data. Since the fiber length in the plastification unit is significantly reduced and this is not shown in the simulation, the fiber lengths are specified as boundary conditions ($a_R = 104$, $a_R = 66$, $a_R = 56$) in the respective process simulation.

Figure 4: Mesh of plate for process simulation (left) and of tensile bar for structural simulation (right)

3.4 Structural Simulation

The simulation of the mechanical test is carried out with the ANSYS MAPDL[®] software from Ansys Inc., Cannonsburg, USA. The mesh is shown in Figure 4 (right) with the selected boundary conditions, a fixed support on the left side (red) and a displacement on the right side (blue).

An elastic as well as an elasto-plastic (bilinear) material model is used, which are calibrated using the coupling tool explained below. In addition, the failure is modelled using a maximum stress criterion. The mechanical properties are carried out according to the experimental specifications for the tensile tests.

3.5 Integrative Simulation

In a new coupling tool (Matlab[®], MathWorks[®] Natick, USA) developed at IKT, the micromechanical models are calculated by using the local process induced microstructure derived from process simulation and transfer the properties to a structural simulation. Therefore the calculated distribution of the fiber orientation, length and concentration is read as input and further processed. This includes the models according to Tandon-Weng [15] for the calculation of the anisotropic stiffness matrix in consideration of the local fiber orientation and the locally averaged fiber length as well as the models according to Kelly and Tyson [18] for the calculation of the strength based on the fiber orientation factor and the locally averaged fiber length [17]. Furthermore, the tool includes a reverse engineering approach described in [20] to calibrate the model parameters. The computed properties are transferred to the mesh for the structure simulation (here: tensile test specimen) by means of a mapping routine based on the Delaunay triangulation [21], which additionally includes a material card reduction. Finally, a solver file with all necessary boundary conditions and analysis settings for the execution of the structure simulation is created.

The existing coupling tool was extended for the following investigations by several functionalities and new approaches as described in [22]. On the one hand, this includes a new approach for the calculation of the fiber orientation factor. The orientation angles (eigenvectors λ_i) and the orientation degrees (eigenvalues e_i) of the local fiber orientation are used to determine a direction dependent fiber orientation factor for each element. This results in three strength values which are used to define an orthotropic failure criterion. On the other hand, the locally predicted fiber concentration based on the process simulation as well as a new approach for the consideration of experimental concentration distributions in the calculation of the micromechanical models are included. Thus, all available information on the predicted fiber microstructure (process simulation) is used to determine the anisotropic properties of the structure simulation. Furthermore, an elasto-plastic material model was added to the tool, which can also be calibrated within the reverse engineering process.

4 RESULTS

The results of the process simulation are first compared with the experimentally determined data in order to verify a proper prediction of the fiber microstructure on the basis of the models used and the associated parameters. Figure 5 (left) shows the fiber orientation for PP-LGF20 along the plate thickness determined by experiments and simulation in the middle of the plate (position B). When comparing the two curves for A_{11} , it can be seen that the fiber orientation in flow direction can generally be predicted with small deviations. Only in the skin areas are more distinct deviations recognizable. The same applies to the prediction of A_{22} in the y-direction, whereas larger deviations occur in the core area. A distinct deviation of more than 30 % can be observed in the core zone for A_{33} in the z-direction (panel thickness). For materials with a higher fiber content, the width of the core layer and the resulting deviations increase significantly.

The prediction of the fiber length can only be verified along the flow path on the basis of the available data. The results shown in Figure 5 (right) at the beginning of the flow path (positions A and B) show a good agreement ($\Delta < 8 \%$) for the number-averaged fiber length and at the end of the flow path (position C) a larger deviation (22 %) of the results with a wrong tendency. A prediction of the weight-average fiber length is not possible in this case.

Figure 5: Fiber orientation at position B (left), comparison of fiber length (right)

A successful calibration or application of the fiber migration model cannot be achieved within the scope of this study, as shown in Figure 6 (left). For the calculation of the mechanical properties, the experimentally determined value distribution is included in the micromechanical modelling. However, the experiments are showing the expected fiber migration in the core layer.

In order to ensure comparability of the following results, the material calibration of the micromechanical model is carried out on the basis of preliminary tests and is not changed in the following. Figure 6 (right) shows the influence of the simulation compared to the experimental fiber orientation on the resulting Young's modulus from the structural simulation. The fiber length and concentration are constant and correspond to the experimental mean value.

Figure 6: Fiber orientation at position B (left), comparison of fiber length (right)

It can be seen that, on the one hand, both results underestimate the Young's modulus and, on the other hand, that the small deviations in the prediction of the fiber orientation have a considerable influence. The present tendency can only be predicted correctly if the experimental fiber orientation is taken into account. A similar result can be seen in the calculated tensile strengths, which are not presented here. For further investigations the experimental fiber orientation is therefore taken into account.

The consideration of the fiber length distribution shows, as known from literature [3], also in the simulation with a given fiber length of approx. 0.7 mm and a dispersion of 100 μm only a small influence. However, the tensile strength values can generally be increased and thus approximated to the experimental results. A similar effect can be seen in the application of the plastic material model. Due to the locally different stress states when using different material models, different results are obtained for the characteristic values. Figure 7 (left) shows the calculated stress-strain diagrams using

the plastic material model and taking the experimental fiber orientation and length distribution into account with a constant fiber content. It can be seen that the two curves of the differently oriented specimens are predicted with only a small deviation. On the basis of the new approach for the consideration of the fiber orientation, the tensile strength can be predicted with a deviation of maximum 11 %.

Figure 7: Stress-strain diagrams (left), comparison of predicted stiffness and strength (right)

However, in transfer to higher filled materials and under holistic consideration of the fiber microstructure, on the basis of the experimental data, no correlation can be determined. The prediction of the respective property with additional consideration of the local fiber concentration shows changing tendencies, as shown in Figure 7 (right). In order to be able to identify the possible causes of these deviations, the micromechanical model has to be recalibrated.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The presented results have shown that individual properties of the fibre microstructure of long fibre reinforced materials can be predicted by process simulation with small deviations. However, even small deviations in the fibre orientation can lead to incorrect tendencies in the prediction of the mechanical properties. Taking the experimental data into account, it could be shown that the newly developed approach can predict strength based on local fibre orientation and length. The achieved deviation is only about 11 % and a renewed calibration suggests a further improvement. Furthermore, it was shown that the developed approach for the holistic consideration of the fibre microstructure could be successfully realized. However, since the results of this method show changing tendencies, a new calibration should be carried out in further studies in order to identify the reasons of these deviations. Furthermore, it is not yet possible to predict the local fiber concentration, hence there is also a strong need for further research.

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